

The Colour of Complex Diazoles

Part II

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In a previous communication an attempt has been made by one of us (Chakravarti, this Journal, 1924, I, 19) to study the colour of compounds containing a condensed pyridine-iminazole ring system in their skeleton. It has already been pointed out that substances having a fused pyrrol-iminazole residue are coloured. The pyridine-iminazole derivatives prepared by Chakravarti (*loc. cit.*) as well as the compound, 1 : 2-*ortho*-benzoylene-acetyl-1 : 3-benziminazole obtained by Bistrzycki and Fässler (Helv. Chim. Acta., 1923, 6, 519) by the condensation of homophthalic anhydride with *ortho*-phenylene diamine were likewise found to be coloured. The present investigation was undertaken with a view to further elucidate the relation between the colour and constitution of the pyridine-iminazole systems. For this purpose camphoric anhydride was condensed severally with *ortho*-phenylene-, 1 : 3 : 4-*ortho*-tolylene-, and 1 : 2-naphthalene diamines. It was anticipated from the behaviour of analogous compounds that the diazoles so derived would all be coloured, but contrary to this expectation it was found that they were all colourless.

A plausible explanation for the absence of colour in these diazoles appears to be that in camphoric anhydride a fully hydrogenised ring system is present, which may account for the hypsochromic effect on the iminazoles

derived from it. But it seems to be an almost established fact that in the compounds of the fluorescein, eosin and rhodamine series derived from camphoric anhydride, the fully hydrogenised 'camphoryl' group has little or no deterrent effect on their colour. From an observation of the colour of these compounds as compared with those of the phthaleins, Sircar and Dutt (Trans. Chem. Soc., 1922, 121, 1283) conclude that the hydrogenised camphoryl residue seem to enhance the chromophoric properties of the dyestuffs obtained rather than cause any diminution in them. Singh, Rai and Lal (*ibid.*, 1922, 121, 1421) from a comparative study of the absorption spectra of the camphoreins and the phthaleins state that the intensity of the colour of the former is only slightly less than that of the latter; whereas phenol-camphorein is admittedly more coloured than phenolphthalein. Evidently, the absence of colour in the camphor-diazoles which contain a piperidine-iminazole ring system cannot be explained by any of the experimental evidences so far obtained. It is, therefore, quite natural to assume that the condensed pyrrol-, pyridine-, and piperidine-iminazoles by themselves do not form the chromophores in the coloured complex diazoles. On the other hand, the colour may be due to the presence in the molecule of a kind of unsaturated linkages like the *ortho*- and *para*-quinonoid structures in benzenoid compounds which on being destroyed by hydrogenation as in the case of the camphor-iminazoles result in the production of colourless compounds. But this view of the structure of these diazoles requires further investigation and cannot be taken without qualification.

Camphoric anhydride condenses with *ortho*-phenylene diamine in alcoholic solution and furnishes a mixture of three phenylene-amidine-trimethyl-*cyclo*-pentane carboxylic acids with melting points 203°, 233°, and 240-42°.

The compound with m. p. 203° solidifies on further raising the temperature above this point and again melts at 242°. Their percentage composition is the same. These compounds are therefore isomeric. Camphoric anhydride might give rise to two isomeric amidine-carboxylic acids in the following manner:—

The acids melting at 233° and 242° are represented by either of the above configurations. What then, represents the third acid melting at 203°? As the latter is transformed into the compound melting at 242° on heating it is evident that the isomerism exhibited in this case is similar to that observed in the case of the camphoric and *iso*-camphoric acids (*Cf.* Ber., 27, 2001, etc.), thus:—

As the physical properties, such as solubility in solvents, etc., of these acids differ very slightly from one another their separation from a mixture containing them and subsequent purification could only be accomplished after considerable difficulty.

On being heated with acetic anhydride each of the above acids loses a molecule of water and is converted into the corresponding diazoles which are found to be

colourless. The diazoles are, therefore, represented by the following diagrams:—

Camphoric anhydride on being similarly treated with 1 : 3 : 4-*ortho*-tolylene diamine yields a mixture of three acids. Two of them are represented by diagrams similar to (I) and (II) shown above, whereas the other differs from the rest by its possessing chloroform of crystallisation instead of alcohol or acetone which the former possess.* These acids also furnish the corresponding diazoles on treatment with acetic anhydride. 1 : 2-Naphthylene diamine and camphoric anhydride condense together in an analogous manner and yield a similar series of compounds.

The condensation of *ortho*-diamines with camphoric anhydride might give rise to several stereo-isomeric acids and the corresponding diazoles, of which only a few have actually been isolated and described. Unless a systematic study of these acids alone is undertaken, no definite formula can be attributed to any of the diazoles. As the

* These compounds as well as the diazoles derived from them have a strong tendency to combine with certain solvents like alcohol, acetone, benzene, toluene, etc., and they refuse to crystallise unless these solvents are present at least in small quantities. This has been determined in some cases by the direct estimation of their carbon and hydrogen contents. The products do not part with these solvents even on strong heating, whereby the compounds themselves are destroyed. On cautious heating the solvents are only partially removed. The difficulty the authors encountered in completely freeing the compounds from their solvents of crystallisation, led them to avoid solvents having tendency to enter into the compounds and crystallise them from light petroleum. Petrol ether was, however, found to be unsuitable as a crystallising medium for the crystallisation of the anhydrous diazoles in all cases and hence only a few of the latter have been described. The solvents entering into combination should more properly be termed *solvent of constitution* rather than that of crystallisation.

purpose of the present investigation was the study of the colour of these diazoles rather than a complete examination of the constitution of all the possible stereoisomeric acids and the corresponding diazoles, the authors thought it unnecessary at this stage to go into details to determine their spatial configurations, it being assumed that the colours of these compounds are in no way dependent on their stereoisomerism. The authors, however, intend to take up a polarimetric study of the acids as this may lead to interesting results.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Condensation of Camphoric Anhydride with ortho-Phenylene Diamine. The Formation of Phenylene-amidine-trimethyl-cyclo-pentane Carboxylic Acids.—3·8 gms. of camphoric anhydride was mixed with 2·6 gms. of *ortho*-phenylene diamine and the mixture dissolved in about 120 c.c. of absolute alcohol. The mixture was heated under reflux for four to five hours and the alcohol distilled off. The pasty residue was washed repeatedly with hot toluene in which the unreacted anhydride and the diamine and also a small portion of the reaction products were soluble (*a*). The mass left behind was dissolved in a small quantity of absolute alcohol and poured into a large volume of water when a granular precipitate was obtained. This was washed repeatedly with anhydrous ether in which a portion dissolved (*b*) leaving behind a crystalline powdery mass of phenylene-amidine-trimethyl-*cyclo*-pentane carboxylic acid melting at 233°(I). (Found: C=70·39; H=7·11; N=10·21. $C_{16}H_{23}N_2O_2$ requires C=70·58; H=7·25; N=10·29 per cent.). The compound is completely soluble in alkaline carbonates and bicarbonates and is precipitated from solution in the form of a light amorphous powder on acidifying with dilute acetic or mineral acids. It is

exceedingly soluble in acetone, chloroform, methyl and ethyl alcohols but insoluble in ether, benzene and toluene.

The ethereal solution (*b*) was evaporated and the residual mass crystallised from methyl alcohol. This amidine carboxylic acid melts at 203° (III). On further-heating it solidifies and melts again at 242° with decomposition (see below). This is an acid and resembles the previous compound in chemical and physical characteristics. (Found: N=10·25. $C_{16}H_{20}N_2O_2$ requires N=10·29 per cent.). The residue left after evaporation of the methyl alcoholic mother-liquor was treated with a solution of sodium carbonate when a small portion remained insoluble, which was crystallised from dilute alcohol, and melted at 132°. The toluene was distilled off from extract (*a*) and the residue washed with dilute sodium carbonate solution (*c*) when a further quantity of the product melting at 132° was obtained. This compound is identical with the diazole described below. The sodium carbonate solution (*c*) on being neutralised with dilute acetic acid yielded a precipitate of a phenylene-amidine-trimethyl-*cyclo*-pentane carboxylic acid, which was crystallised from alcohol. It melted at 238° to 242°* with decomposition (II). (Found N=10·41. $C_{16}H_{20}N_2O_2$ requires N=10·20 per cent.). That the acids (I) and (II) are different has been settled by a mixed melting point determination. In fact, the m. p. of an equivalent mixture of the two was considerably lower than that of either of the original substances. The diazole obtained from acid (II) was found to be identical with that from acid (III) (*vide infra*). The diazoles from (I) and (II) were distinctly different. with m. p.'s 132° and 138°

* The melting points of these acids were never so definite as represented above. The temperatures slightly vary according to the duration of heating owing to the formation of the corresponding diazoles which are all of lower melting points.

respectively. The mixed melting point of these two diazoles was also found to be much below their individual melting points.

When camphoric anhydride and *ortho*-phenylene diamine were fused together between 150° and 160° for half-an-hour, the major product was the acid melting at 242° together with a fairly large amount of diazole (*vide infra*); when, however, the condensation was carried on in alcoholic solution, the predominant portion was the acid with m. p. 233°. In both these reactions a small amount of the *ortho*-phenylene-diamine-camphorein is always formed which gives an intense red coloration in acid solution turning into yellow on adding alkalis. The compound was not further studied.

Diazole derived from compound (II).—The amidine carboxylic acid m. p. 233° was heated under reflux with excess of acetic anhydride for about two hours and the solution on cooling poured into a large volume of water and treated with excess of sodium carbonate. The semi-solid mass obtained was dissolved in a minimum quantity of alcohol and precipitated by water containing a little sodium carbonate, whereby a crystalline product melting at 132° was obtained. (Found: C=70.06; H=8.20; N=8.05. $C_{16}H_{18}N_2O$, $1\frac{1}{2}C_2H_5OH$ requires C=70.58; H=8.36; N=8.66 per cent.).

Diazole derived from Compound (III).—This diazole was obtained in a similar manner from the acid m. p. 203° and melted at 138°. (Found: N=8.59. $C_{16}H_{18}N_2O$, $1\frac{1}{2}C_2H_5OH$ requires N=8.66 per cent.). The diazole from compound II was prepared in an analogous manner and was found to melt at 138° and to be identical with that obtained from (III).

The *diazole* isolated from the products of fusion of the anhydride and the diamine was crystallised from

light petroleum and melted at 77°. (Found N=11.22. $C_{16}H_{18}N_2O$ requires N=11.02 per cent.).

The *diazole* derived from compound (I) m. p. 233° when extracted and purified with light petroleum instead of alcohol melted at 95°. (Found: N=11.09. $C_{16}H_{18}N_2O$ requires N=11.02 per cent.).

Condensation of Camphoric Anhydride with 1 : 3 : 4:—ortho-Tolylene Diamine—The Formation of Tolylenamidine-trimethyl-cyclo-pentane Carboxylic acids.—6 grams of the anhydride and 4 grams of the diamine were boiled together with 150 c.c. of absolute alcohol for 5 hours. The alcohol was distilled off and the residue extracted with hot toluene repeatedly (*d*). The final residue was dissolved in a minimum quantity of alcohol and precipitated by adding the solution to a large volume of water. The precipitate was dried, dissolved in acetone and treated with excess of ether. An acid slowly crystallised out on standing which was washed with ether and melted at 239-40° (compare formula I). (Found: C=65.00; N=6.32. $C_{17}H_{22}N_2O_2$, $3(CH_3)_2CO$ requires C=65.09; N=6.60 per cent.). The mother-liquor on evaporation and treatment with acetone and ether for a second time gave a further product which was recrystallised from a mixture of chloroform and ether. This acid melts at 228-29° and contains chloroform of crystallisation. (Found: N=6.16. $C_{17}H_{22}N_2O_2$, $1\frac{1}{2}CHCl_3$ requires N=6.02 per cent.).

The toluene from extract (*d*) was distilled off and the residue treated with dilute sodium carbonate solution. A portion remained insoluble which was extracted with petroleum ether; the portion insoluble in the latter is supposed to be the tolylene-diamine-camphorein because like its phenylene analogue it gave characteristic colour reactions with acids and alkalis. The petroleum solution was evaporated, the viscous residue dissolved in

alcohol and purified by pouring into a large volume of water. This was found to be identical with the diazole melting at 97° . The portion of the extract (*d*) which dissolved in sodium carbonate solution was neutralised with dilute acetic acid and the precipitate crystallised from 50–60 % alcohol. The crystals melt at $250-52^{\circ}$ (compare formula II). (Found: N = 6.49. $C_{17}H_{22}N_2O_2$ $3C_2H_5OH$ requires N = 6.60 per cent.).

Diazoles derived from Toluene-amidine-trimethyl-cyclo-pentane-carboxylic acids.—Each of the acids with m. p. $239-40^{\circ}$ and $250-52^{\circ}$ were boiled with excess of acetic anhydride and the diazoles were isolated in a manner exactly similar to the phenylene compounds (*vide supra*). They were colourless and melted at 93° and 97° respectively and contained alcohol of crystallisation. They lose alcohol partially on heating and even in a vacuum desiccator. They were therefore air dried and analysed. (Found: N = 6.62, 6.70. $C_{17}H_{22}N_2O$, $3C_2H_5OH$ requires N = 6.89 per cent.).

Condensation of Camphoric Anhydride with 1:2-Naphthylene Diamine. The Formation of Naphthylene amidine-trimethyl-cyclo-pentane Carboxylic Acids.—Equimolecular quantities of the anhydride and the diamine were boiled together in absolute alcohol for 5 hours. The alcohol was distilled off, the residue washed with hot toluene, dissolved in alcohol and precipitated by water. The precipitate was washed thoroughly with water and dissolved in dilute sodium carbonate solution. Two different colourless amidine carboxylic acids were obtained by fractional precipitation of the solution with acids. They were further purified by solution in alcohol and precipitation with water. One acid (compare formula I) had the melting point $180-82^{\circ}$ (Found: N = 8.63. $C_{20}H_{23}N_2O_2$ requires N = 8.69 per cent.). The other acid melted at 235° with decomposition. (Found:

$N=7.06$ $C_{20}H_{22}N_2O_2$, $1\frac{1}{2}C_2H_5OH$ requires $N=7.16$ per cent.).

The Diazole.—The acid with m.p. $180-82^\circ$ was as before treated with acetic anhydride and the diazole was obtained like its previous analogues and melted at $80-82^\circ$. (Found: $N=8.09$. $C_{20}H_{22}N_2O$, C_2H_5OH requires $N=8.00$ per cent.).

In conclusion, the authors beg to express their great indebtedness to Sir P. C. Ray for his kind interest and encouragement during the progress of the investigation and lastly to Mr. K. C. Ray for rendering occasional help in the analytical part of the work.

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[Received Nov. 27, 1924.]
